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Research Article

Development and Validation Of UV-Visible Spectroscopic Methods for The Quantification and Forced Degradation Profile of New Antipsychotic Drug Lumateperone in Bulk and Pharmaceutical Dosage Form

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ABSTRACT

This abstract outline the development and validation of UV-visible spectroscopic method for quantification and forced degradation of lumateperone in pharmaceutical dosage forms. Method development involves optimizing chromatographic conditions, while validation ensures the method's accuracy, precision, linearity, and robustness. Lumateperone is a medication used to manage and treat schizophrenia and other neuropsychiatric disorders. It is a second-generation atypical antipsychotic medication that exhibits a novel mechanism of action. This activity describes the indications, mechanism of action, and administration of lumateperone as a valuable treatment of schizophrenia.

INTRODUCTION

Lumateperone, sold under the brand name Caplyta, is an atypical antipsychotic medication of the butyrophenone class. It is approved for the treatment of schizophrenia as well as bipolar depression, Lumateperone was approved for medical use in the United States in December 2019 with an initial indication for schizophrenia and became available in February 2020. It has since demonstrated efficacy in bipolar depression and

received FDA approval in December 2021 for depressive episodes associated with both bipolar I and II disorders. Lumateperone acts as an antagonist at 5-HT_{2A} receptors and binds to several dopamine receptors (D₁, D₂, and D₄) with moderate affinity. It has moderate serotonin transporter reuptake inhibition, which is partly responsible for its antidepressant effect in bipolar disorder and reduction of negative symptoms of schizophrenia.

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Fig. 1 Structure of Lumateperone

Table 1. Drug profile

Sr. no	PARAMETERS	LUMATEPERONE
1	Molecular Formula	C ₃₁ H ₃₆ FN ₃ O ₄ S
2	Molecular Weight	565.7 g/mole
3	Synonym	ITI-007Tosylate, ITI-722
4	Category	Atypical antipsychotic
5	Solubility	Soluble in Organic Solvent (Ethanol, DMSO) Sparingly Soluble in Aqueous Buffers Slightly Soluble in Water
6	CAS NUMBER	1187020-80-9
7	Mechanism of action	Lumateperone acts as an antagonist at 5-HT _{2A} receptors and binds to several dopamine receptors (D ₁ D ₂ and D ₄) with moderate affinity. It has moderate serotonin transporter reuptake inhibition, which is partly responsible for its antidepressant effect in bipolar disorder and reduction of negative symptoms of schizophrenia.
8	Melting Point	182-183°C
9	Use	To Treat Schizophrenia & Bipolar depression.
10	Adverse Effects	Dry mouth, wheezing.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Material

Drug sample used

Pharmaceutically pure sample of LUMATEPERONE TOSYLATE were obtained from Alkem Laboratories, Mumbai.

Fig. 2 Drug sample

Chemicals and Solvents:

All the chemicals and solvents used were of analytical grade. The solvent system used for the study composed of –

- Methanol
- Water

As a ratio methanol: water (70:30)

Manufacturing of immediate release LUMATEPERONE TABLETS (42mg) is carried out by the following formula for conducting 2 batches of 10, 50 tablets

Pharmaceutical Formulation:

Batch 1. LT1

Batch 2. LT2

Fig. 3 Pharmaceutical formulation

Instrument

Double beam UV-Visible Spectrophotometer Shimadzu 1900 using UV Probe Software. The spectra were recorded over range 200 - 400 nm against solvent in 1 cm Quarts cells.

Fig.4 Double Beam UV- Visible Spectrophotometer

Table 2. Formulation Table:

Ingredient	Percent amounts	Wt. for each tablet (mg)	Batch 1 for 10 Tblts. (mg)	Batch 2 for 50 Tblts. (mg)
Lumateperone	20%	42	420	2100
Mannitol	73.7%	154.77	1547.7	7738.5
Crospovidone	5.0%	10.5	105	525
Talc	0.30%	0.63	6.3	31.5
Magnesium stearate	1.0%	2.1	2.1	105

Fig.5: Drug & Excipients

Table 3. Quality control test for formulated tablets

Test	Standard	Test Sample	Inference
Appearance	Free from defects	Free from defects	Compliance with Std.
Hardness	4 to 8 kp	5.2 kp	Compliance with Std.
Thickness	2.5 to 4mm	2.7mm	Compliance with Std.
Weight variation	7.5%	-6.09% to 5.23%	Compliance with Std.
Friability	NMT 1%	0.232	Compliance with Std.
Disintegration Test	NMT 15 min	Less than 1min	Compliance with Std.
Dissolution Test 1	NLT 75%	79%	Compliance with Std.
Dissolution Test 2	NLT 75%	82%	Compliance with Std.

Fig. 5 Dissolution test Graph

Method Development

In the present work, an attempt was made to develop and validate a simple, precise and accurate method for the estimation of LUMATEPERONE in pure bulk form and in pharmaceutical dosage form by UV - Visible Spectroscopy.

Selection of solvent system:

The solubility of drugs was determined in a variety of polar to non-polar solvents as per Indian Pharmacopeial standards. We performed trial and error method to select the best possible solvent which can dissolve both drugs and tablet

formulation. By performing solubility studies of LUMATEPERONE in different solvents and its ratios, observing results we concluded best solvent system was Methanol: water in the ratios 70:30 respectively.

Fig. 6 Trail & error method for solvent selection.

Preparation of Standard Stock Solution:

Accurately weighed 10 mg of Lumateperone were transferred into a clean & dried 100 ml volumetric flasks separately and then volume was made up to the mark with solvent Methanol: water (70:30) to get a standard concentration of 100 µg/ml. This standard stock solution (100 µg/ml) was further diluted with solvent system to obtain a series of dilution - 10, 20, 30, 40, and 50µg/ml for Lumateperone.

Accurately weighed 52 mg of tablet powder equivalent to 10 mg of lumateperone were transferred into a clean & dried 100 ml volumetric flasks separately and then volume was made up to the mark with solvent Methanol: water (70:30) to get a standard concentration of 100 µg/ml. This standard stock solution (100 µg/ml) was further diluted with solvent system to obtain a series of dilution - 10, 20, 30, 40, and 50µg/ml for Lumateperone.

Fig.7 Stock & Dilutions of API

Fig.8 Stock & Dilutions of Tablets
Determination of Maximum Wavelength (λ_{max})

Preparation of Standard Test Solution

The standard solution and also for test solution dilution having highest concentration was scanned at 200 nm to 400 nm with diluent as the blank to detect maximum wavelength.

Fig.9 Estimation of Maxima of Lumateperone

From the above (Figure-) spectra of Lumateperone standard solution wavelength

maxima identified for quantification were 313 nm (λ_{max})

Fig. 10 Estimation of Maxima of Lumateperone

From the above (Figure-) spectra of Lumateperone Test solution wavelength maxima identified for quantification were 313 nm (λ_{max}).

Bulk formulation obtained is 0.994 & for pharmaceutical formulation obtained is 0.997. The plot is a straight line and the results are tabulated in the Table.

Method Validation

Linearity & Range

Prepare a series of standard Lumateperone solutions and Test solution of lumateperone of having concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 40 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, and 50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ each. Measure the absorbance of each standard solution at the determined (λ_{max}). Plot the absorbance values against the corresponding concentrations. A linear regression curve was constructed, the correlation coefficient (R^2) and assessment value calculated. The correlation coefficient (R^2) for Lumateperone

Table 4. Linearity and Range

Sr. No.	Standard Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance @313nm	Correlation Coefficient
1	10	0.072	0.994 Limit \geq 0.999
2	20	0.148	
3	30	0.223	
4	40	0.327	
5	50	0.429	
6	60	0.536	

Sr. No.	Test Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance @313nm	Correlation Coefficient
1	10	0.083	0.997 Limit ≥ 0.999
2	20	0.174	
3	30	0.264	
4	40	0.370	
5	50	0.441	

Fig.10 Linearity graph of Bulk formulation

Fig.11 Linearity graph of Pharmaceutical Formulation

Precision

Express the closeness of agreement between a series of measurements obtained from multiple sampling of the same homogeneous sample under the prescribed conditions. Precision is usually expressed as the standard deviation (SD) or relative standard deviation (%RSD).

Repeatability

To check the degree of repeatability, standard solution containing Lumateperone were taken six times separately of the same concentration 10µg/ml and was analyzed. The standard deviation (S.D.) and Percent Relative Standard Deviation (% R.S.D.) was calculated and given in Table 5 & 6.

Table.5 Repeatability of API

Sr. no.	Conc taken	Absorbance	Average	SD	%RSD
1	10	0.083	0.081	0.001	1.999 Limit < 2%
2	10	0.082			
3	10	0.080			
4	10	0.080			
5	10	0.084			
6	10	0.081			

Table.6 Repeatability of Tablets

Sr. no	Conc. taken	Absorbance	Averages	SD	%RSD
1	10	0.083	0.083	0.001	1.769 Limit < 2%
2	10	0.085			
3	10	0.084			
4	10	0.084			

5	10	0.081			
6	10	0.082			

Intra-day precision

Assessed by analysing multiple replicates of the same sample on the same day, under the same conditions. The % RSD due to Lumateperone

concentration for samples for standard solution was found to be 1.825. The % RSD due to concentration for Lumateperone the assay meets the requirements. Results are tabulated in the Table 7.

Table 7. Intra Precision of API

Sr No.	Sample reading	Sample concentration	Absorbance	Mean	Standard Deviation	%RSD
1.	Morning	10 µg/ml	0.082	0.083	0.001	1.825% Limit < 2%
2.	Afternoon	10 µg/ml	0.084			
3.	Evening	10 µg/ml	0.085			

The % RSD due to Lumateperone concentration for samples for standard solution was found to be 1.840. The % RSD due to concentration for

Lumateperone the assay meets the requirements. Results are tabulated in the Table 8.

Table 8. Intra Precision of Tablets

Sr. No.	Sample reading	Sample concentration	Absorbance	Mean	Standard Deviation	%RSD
1.	Morning	10 µg/ml	0.083	0.084	0.001	1.840% Limit < 2%
2.	Afternoon	10 µg/ml	0.085			
3.	Evening	10 µg/ml	0.086			

Inter-day precision (Intermediate Precision)

Assessed by analysing multiple replicates of the same sample on different days, by different

analysts, or using different equipment within the same laboratory. The %RSD due to Lumateperone concentration for the three samples was found to be 1.847% & 1.825%.

Table 9. Inter-day Precision of API

Sr. No.	Sample reading	Sample concentration	Absorbance	Mean	Standard Deviation	%RSD
1.	Day 1	10 µg/ml	0.081	0.082	0.001	1.847% Limit < 2%
2.	Day 2	10 µg/ml	0.083			
3.	Day 3	10 µg/ml	0.084			

Table 10. Inter-day Precision of Tablets

Sr. No.	Sample reading	Sample concentration	Absorbance	Mean	Standard Deviation	%RSD
1.	Day 1	10 µg/ml	0.083	0.084	0.001	1.825% Limit < 2%
2.	Day 2	10 µg/ml	0.085			
3.	Day 3	10 µg/ml	0.086			

Accuracy

This parameter determines the accuracy of the assay results under the same operating conditions test. A sample was constituted analysed for the accuracy with known quantity of standard samples of Lumateperone at 50%, 100%, 150% concentration levels and assayed as per the method stated under analytical Methods respectively. Three determinations were performed under each concentration levels respectively. Results are

shown in Tables 11, 12, 13. The % RSD due to recovery of Lumateperone at 50%, 100%, 150% concentration levels were found to be 0.40%, 0.38% and 0.30% respectively. Nine sample preparations were analyzed according to the proposed method of analysis. The % RSD due to Lumateperone concentration for the assay meets the requirements and within 98.0% to 102%. Results are tabulated in the Table 11 & 12.

Table 11. Accuracy and Recovery Results @ 50% Concentration level

Sr. No.	Accuracy @ 50% level	Amount Added	Absorbance	Amount Recovered	% Recovery	% RSD
1	Sample Preparation -1	10 µg/ml	0.208	9.76	99.37%	1.99% Limit < 2%
2	Sample Preparation -2		0.203	10.15		
3	Sample Preparation -3		0.200	9.90		

Table 12. Accuracy and Recovery Results @ 100 % Concentration level

Sr. No.	Accuracy @ 100% level	Amount Added	Absorbance	Amount Recovered	% Recovery	% RSD
1	Sample Preparation -1	20 µg/ml	0.405	19.76	99.60%	0.85% Limit < 2%
2	Sample Preparation -2		0.412	20.10		
3	Sample Preparation -3		0.408	19.90		

Table 13. Accuracy and Recovery Results @ 150% Concentration level

Sr. No.	Accuracy @ 150% level	Amount Added	Absorbance	Amount Recovered	% Recovery	% RSD
1	Sample Preparation -1	30 µg/ml	0.608	29.66	99.70%	0.80% Limit < 2%
2	Sample Preparation -2		0.618	30.15		
3	Sample Preparation -3		0.613	29.90		

Robustness

Assess the capacity of the method to remain unaffected by small but deliberate variations in method parameters (e.g., wavelength, solvent composition, temperature). Make small changes to

the method parameters and observe the effect on the absorbance of a standard solution. The method should remain reliable even with these small variations. The respective test assay results of Lumateperone having concentration as 10 µg/ml was illustrious. The result is expressed as shown in table 14 & 15.

Table 14. Robustness of API

Sr. No.	Wavelength (nm)	Absorbance	Mean	Standard Deviation	%RSD
1.	243nm	0.356	0.349	0.006	0.1789
		0.347			
		0.344			
2.	280nm	0.107	0.105	0.002	1.904
		0.105			
		0.103			
3.	340nm	0.056	0.057	0.001	1.754
		0.057			
		0.058			

Table 15. Robustness of Tablets

Sr. No.	Wavelength (nm)	Absorbance	Mean	Standard Deviation	%RSD
1.	243nm	0.079	0.077	0.001	1.966
		0.078			
		0.076			
2.	280nm	0.078	0.079	0.001	1.265
		0.079			
		0.078			
3.	340nm	0.077	0.077	0.001	1.975
		0.076			
		0.079			

Ruggedness

The degree of reproducibility of test results obtained by the analysis of the same sample in different laboratories, by different analysts, using different instruments, different reagents, and/or

different days. The respective test assay results of Lumateperone having concentration as 10 µg/ml was illustrious. The result is expressed as shown in table 16 & 17.

Table 16. Ruggedness of API

Sr. No.	Analyst	Absorbance	Mean	Standard Deviation	%RSD
1.	Analyst - I	0.072	0.072	0.001	1.388
2.	Analyst - II	0.071			Limit
3.	Analyst - III	0.073			< 2%

Table 17. Ruggedness of Tablets

Sr. No.	Analyst	Absorbance	Mean	Standard Deviation	%RSD
1.	Analyst - I	0.083	0.081	0.001	1.413
2.	Analyst - II	0.081			Limit
3.	Analyst - III	0.081			< 2%

Limit of Detection(LOD)

The lowest amount of analyte in a sample that can be detected but not necessarily quantitated as an exact value. It can be calculated using the formula: $LOD = 3.3 \times (SD/Slope)$, where SD is the standard deviation of the response (y-intercepts of regression lines or standard deviations of blank determinations) and Slope is the slope of the calibration curve.

$$LOD = 3.3 \times (0.002/0.025) = 0.264 \mu\text{g/ml. (for API)}$$

$$LOD = 3.3 \times (0.001/0.032) = 0.103 \mu\text{g/ml. (for tablets)}$$

Limit of Quantitation (LOQ)

The lowest amount of analyte in a sample that can be quantitatively determined with suitable precision and accuracy. It can be calculated using the formula: $LOQ = 10 \times (SD/Slope)$, where SD is the standard deviation of the response (y-intercepts

of regression lines or standard deviations of blank determinations) and Slope is the slope of the calibration curve.

$$LOQ = 10 \times (0.002/0.025) = 0.8 \mu\text{g/ml. (for API)}$$

$$LOQ = 10 \times (0.001/0.032) = 0.312 \mu\text{g/ml. (for Tablets)}$$

Assay of Lumateperone in its formulation

For analysis of commercial formulations of Tablets, 10 tablets were weighed, powdered and accurately weighed the equivalent to 10mg of Lumateperone, which was transferred into 100 ml volumetric flask and make up to 100ml with methanol: water (70:30), filtered and further diluted with methanol: water (70:30) to get the concentrations within the linearity range 10-50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and measured at 313 nm for Lumateperone. Then the amount of drug present in the formulations was calculated. The results were shown in Table 18.

Table 18. Results of Assay

Drug	Label Claim (mg/tab)	Amount Estimated	% Label Claim	% Deviation
Lumateperone	42	40.7	96.90%	-3.1%

Derivative spectroscopy

Derivative spectra amplify subtle changes in the slope of the original spectrum. For a single component, this can help in precisely determining the wavelength of maximum absorbance (λ_{max}) and reveal underlying shoulders or fine structures

that might be obscured in the zero-order spectrum. Smoothing techniques are applied to the original (zero-order) spectrum *before* or *during* the calculation of the derivative. The goal is to reduce the high-frequency noise while preserving the underlying spectral features of the single components.

Fig. 12 Smoothing of lumateperone spectra

First Derivative: The first derivative spectrum shows a zero crossing at the λ_{max} of the original peak. It also exhibits a maximum and a minimum at the inflection points of the zero-order band.

Fig.13 1st order derivative

Second Derivative: The second derivative spectrum typically displays a negative peak at the λ_{max} of the original band and positive satellite peaks on either side. The sharpness of this negative peak can provide a more accurate determination of λ_{max} , especially for broad bands.

Fig. 14 2nd order derivative

STRSS DEGRADATION STUDIES:

Acidic Degradation:

5ml of stock solution of Lumateperone, and 5 ml of 2 N HCl were added in 10 ml of volumetric flask

and the volumetric flask was kept at 80°C for 3-hour reflux and left them for the 30 minutes. Afterwards the absorbance of solution was analysed separately at wavelength max 313nm given

Fig.15 Graph of acidic degradation

Alkali Degradation

5 ml of stock solution of Lumateperone and 5 ml of 2 N NaOH was added in 10 ml of volumetric flask and the volumetric flask was kept at 80 c for 3 Hours reflux and left them for the 30 minutes. Afterwards the absorbance of solution was analysed separately at wavelength max 313nm.

Fig.16 Graph of Alkali Degradation

Dry Heat Induced Degradation:

Lumateperone sample was taken in a Petri plate and exposed to a temperature of 50°C for 3 hours

in an oven. After 3 hours, 10 mg of the sample was diluted with methanol: water (70:30) to 10 ml. From this solution, dilution was done to achieve the appropriate concentration (5µg/ml)

Fig.17 Graph of dry heat induced degradation

Oxidative Degradation

Applying 3% of hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) at room temperature (25°C) and left them for the 3

hour. Afterwards the absorbance of solution were analyses separately at wavelength max 313nm. (Graph)

Fig.18 Graph of oxidative degradation

Sunlight Degradation

Lumateperone sample was taken in a Petri plate and exposed to sunlight for 3 hrs. 10 mg of the

sample was diluted with methanol: water (70:30) up to 10 ml. From this solution, dilution was done to achieve the appropriate concentration (5µg/ml)

Fig. 19 Graph of Sunlight degradation

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

The method discussed in the present work provides a simple, stable, rapid, accurate, precise, reliable, less expensive (Economical), time saving

and convenient method for the analysis of LUMATEPERONE using U.V. Spectrophotometry. The results were shown in Table 19.

Table 19. Result of API & Tablets

Sr. No.	Parameter	Results for API	Results for Tablets
1.	Absorbance Maxima (nm)	313nm	313nm
2.	Linearity & Range	10-60 µg/ml	10-50 µg/ml
3.	Regression equation	y=0.071x+0.018	y = 0.0091x - 0.0072
4.	Correlation Coefficient (R ²)	0.9944	R ² = 0.9973
5.	Repeatability	1.999	1.769%

5.	Intra precision %RSD	1.825%	1.840%
6.	Inter-day precision %RSD	1.847%	1.825%
7.	% Recovery at 50%	99.37%	
8.	% Recovery at 100%	99.60%	
9.	% Recovery at 150%	99.70%	
10.	Robustness %RSD at 243nm	0.1789%	1.966%
11.	Robustness %RSD at 280nm	1.904%	1.265%
12.	Robustness %RSD at 295 nm	1.754%	1.975%
13.	Ruggedness %RSD	1.388	1.413
14.	LOD	0.264	0.103
15.	LOQ	0.8	0.312
16.	%Label Claim	96.90%	

Table 20. degradation study results

Stress condition	Time	Observation	Degradation
Acidic Degradation	RT for 3hr	λ_{\max} shifted	0.319%
Alkali Degradation	RT for 3hr	λ_{\max} shifted	12.34%
Dry Heat Induced Degradation	50°C 3hr	λ_{\max} Not shifted	0.4%
Oxidative degradation	RT for 3hr	λ_{\max} Shifted	9.46%
Sunlight Degradation	For 3hr	λ_{\max} Not shifted	0%

CONCLUSION:

The presented method was validated in terms of reproducibility, sensitivity, accuracy, precision and detection of limits in accordance with internationally accepted guideline, which can be directly easily applied to the analysis of pharmaceutical dosage form of Lumateperone. This method can be used for the routine quality control of the drug in bulk as well as in pharmaceutical formulations. Although no attempt has been made to identify the degradation products of the pharmaceutical dosage form of Lumateperone, the proposed method can still be utilized for stability-indicating analysis. The proposed method can be used as a stability indicating method for assay of Lumateperone in bulk dosage form as well as pharmaceutical formulations and therapeutic drug monitoring of schizophrenic patient.

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